

FROM E-LEARNING RESOURCES PROSPECTS FOR USE

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Annotation: the article presents technologies for creating e-learning resources and their implementation in improving educational processes. There is an advantage of electronic presentation when it is possible to quickly correct the shortcomings of educational material, make the necessary changes, prepare the material in different ways with the help of a computer, use color images, make them possible to move.

Keywords: electronic, educational, resource, computer, medium, educational, hypertext, graphic table.

The progress of the comprehensive reforms carried out in our Republic also has a positive impact on the education system directly. Therefore, the implementation of comprehensive reforms in the field, the introduction of international experiments and innovative technologies in order to achieve greater efficiency in all branches of education is becoming more important in the conditions of today's New Uzbekistan.

The fundamental reforms carried out in our country, the development of Science and technology and the requirements for the transition to an informed society are leading to a change in educational strategies. New forms of continuing education have emerged, including networked, informative, distance and innovative educational technologies based on modern teaching technologies. The main reason for the emergence of new types of Education based on information and Communication Technologies is the ability to provide knowledge to people of different classes of society, to systematically increase their qualifications and

successfully solve the tasks of retraining, to limit the possibilities of traditional methods and Means formed over the years of the former educational system.

The creation of an e-learning resource includes individualization and differentiation of the educational process, control and proper orientation of the student's educational activities on their own, saving training time due to the use of computing capabilities of the computer, visualizing educational materials, modeling the educational processes under study, imitating them, forming optimal decision-making skills in various pedagogical situations, developing a, knowledge gives opportunities such as the formation of a culture of activity.

One software widely used in the creation of e-learning resources is the Ispring program. Usually, in the process of preparing for the presentation, in most cases, Microsoft - PowerPoint software is used. But such presentations can only be in the format of this product (ppt, pptx). Currently, as a result of the development of internet technologies and, in turn, the emergence of a type of distance education, it is necessary to have a file created in flash (swf) format or HTML 5 technology for direct viewing of presentation files online in the internet browser itself. By now, programs have been created that allow you to form a flash roller from a prepared presentation in the Power Point program.

In the educational system electron education as the main reason for the popularization of the use of resources, we can show that there are aspects that are convenient not only for educators, but also for students. For example, students will be able to receive education without themselves wanting to and at any time. In addition to electron education in education through the use of resources the following:

in regions where there is a shortage of pedagogical personnel, students can also be educated online or in a distance form;

learn, search, disseminate and use information about the science that teachers and students want to learn from their internet network;

electronic education in the system to increase the efficiency of education, reduce the consumption of time and funds based on the use of resources;

by applying electron educational resources to the learning process, students will have opportunities, not just to master the subjects, but to what extent they are mastering knowledge and are ready for problem situations, as well as the formation of critical thinking in them, as well as the orientation of students to develop their ability to work on their own independently.

Today, the main factor in the active penetration of electron resources into the educational process is that it is of particular importance with its effectiveness in changing the quality of classes in a positive way. In further improving such quality levels, the development of new strategic projects for the application of various means of training and electron education resources, as well as the establishment of centers containing training rooms, laboratories, mediastudios equipped with digital devices with high efficiency serve as an important factor. The process of organizing classes using e-learning resources, in which students receive the knowledge they receive not only through hearing, but also through visual sensations, effectively contributes to a deep understanding of the idea and content of concepts.

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